

Structuring Healthcare for Success: A Comparative Look at Centralized and Decentralized Models

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Abstract

With healthcare systems under increasing strain, understanding how governance structures impact service quality and accessibility is crucial for shaping effective, sustainable policy reforms. This literature review examines centralized and decentralized health delivery models across Canada, focusing on efficiency, cost, innovation, management, communication, patient experience, and health outcomes. Centralized systems, such as single provincial health authorities, promise streamlined administration, lower non-clinical costs, and standardized practices that enhance electronic health record integration and facilitate the spread of initiatives across the province. These standardized procedures can strengthen accountability and lessen variances in care delivery. In contrast, decentralized models, such as those seen in British Columbia's regional health authorities and independently managed institutions offer greater local autonomy, flexibility, and tailored responses to community-specific challenges. This regionalized approach can foster innovation and ensure services are customized to meet the unique needs of diverse populations. By analyzing the strengths and limitations of both models, this review offers insights to guide policymakers in identifying the most effective structures and strategies for provincial healthcare delivery.

Key words: Centralization, Decentralization, Canadian Healthcare, Efficiency, Cost, Innovation, Flexibility, Communication

Introduction

Healthcare systems worldwide are facing escalating challenges from financial constraints and demographic shifts to demands for enhanced quality and equity. In Canada and other Organization for Economic Co-operation and Development (OECD) countries, debates persist over the optimal balance between centralized and decentralized governance. Decentralization in healthcare systems involves the transfer of power and authority from a higher central government level to a lower provincial or regional level to be managed closer to where users access services. This literature review integrates the insights from twelve key studies to examine how variations in health system structure impact service quality, cost efficiency, innovation, management, and communication. While centralized models promise streamlined administration, uniform quality standards, and economies of scale, decentralized models are credited with local responsiveness, tailored service delivery, and the potential for innovation driven by community-specific needs. The review explores the underlying assumptions and historical evolution of these governance approaches, drawing on empirical evidence and theoretical models to inform policymaking in Canada. Some may view centralization and decentralization as opposing system models, but we argue that the reality is more nuanced and both may exist in harmony or at odds with each other, depending on how they are executed.

Decentralization is described as “The delegation of power from a central authority to regional and local authorities” (Merriam-Webster, 2025). As an intervention, decentralization can

take several forms: devolution, where independent local governments gain control; decentralization, where administrative responsibilities shift to regional offices of the central government; delegation, where semi-independent entities operate under central oversight; and privatization, where private organizations manage public services through contracts (Abimbola et al., 2019). Alternatively, Abimbola et al note that decentralization can be understood as a natural state of governance, where power is inherently dispersed rather than centralized by default.

Centralization, in contrast, consolidates decision-making at the national or provincial level, whether imposed by governments, monarchies, or colonial rulers, or emerging organically as smaller jurisdictions pool resources for efficiency, standardization, or shared public goods like infrastructure and immunization programs (Abimbola et al., 2019). Understanding these structures is key to evaluating how health systems balance efficiency, equity, and adaptability.

Across multiple industries—including banking, energy, aviation, oil and gas, and healthcare—organizational performance has been shown to depend heavily on the alignment between decision-making structures, knowledge flows, and communication systems. Research demonstrates that effective governance, whether centralized or decentralized, enhances system performance when it is matched to environmental uncertainty, asset specificity, and the distribution of knowledge within the network. Studies in service industries and financial institutions have shown that intangible assets such as brand equity, service quality, customer loyalty, and employee communication strongly influence organizational outcomes (Esmacili, 2009a, 2009b, 2010a, 2010b, 2011a, 2011b; Abbasi et al., 2012; Esmacili, 2013a, 2013b, 2013c, 2016). Additional work in the oil and gas sector, energy industry, public-sector organizations, and

supplier selection also emphasizes that knowledge management, organizational structure, and communication clarity are essential drivers of efficiency and performance (Esmaeili, 2013c; Esmaeili & Rayatdost, 2013; Esmaeili, 2018). Studies on digital communication and e-marketing further highlight the role of information systems and customer knowledge in shaping organizational outcomes (Esmaeili & Ruzafzun, 2009). More recent contributions analyzing international franchise governance, decision rights, and control mechanisms demonstrate that the balance between centralization and decentralization influences performance through information-processing, knowledge transfer, and relational communication structures (Esmaeili et al., 2021; Esmaeili & Windsperger, 2022; Esmaeili, 2021). These findings are reinforced by evidence from the healthcare sector, where comparative analyses of centralized and decentralized governance models show that structural alignment and effective communication systems are critical for performance, responsiveness, and service quality (Esmaeili & Sims, 2025). Altogether, this body of research underscores that understanding organizational structure—particularly the allocation of centralization and decentralization—is essential for enhancing system performance across sectors. Whether in banking, franchising, airlines, oil and gas, or healthcare, system success depends on how well organizations design decision-making systems, manage knowledge assets, and build communication frameworks capable of supporting complex operational demands.

Purpose & Scope

This review examines existing literature to analyze the benefits, drawbacks, and key characteristics of centralized and decentralized approaches to universal healthcare delivery,

assessing their impact on desired outcomes. It explores the values, organizational models, and communication strategies that policymakers can leverage to drive meaningful change within Canadian healthcare systems. Additionally, this review identifies gaps and opportunities for future research in the Canadian context. The primary focus is on provincial and territorial healthcare models in Canada, with comparisons to OECD countries. Literature focused on privatized health systems or disease-specific delivery models was excluded.

Methods

The review material was sourced using a range of keywords, including “centralized/centralization”, “decentralized/decentralization”, “Canada/Canadian”, “healthcare”, “communication”, “innovation”, “efficiency”, “cost”, “organizational”, “health outcomes”. The reviewed studies employ a range of methodologies from simultaneous non-linear equations (Dougherty et al., 2022), multiple linear regression analyses (Durmus, 2024), decision space analysis (Marchildon 2019a), realist syntheses (Abimbola et al., 2019), qualitative case studies (Martin et al., 2018, Blanken et al., 2022, Jarvis et al., 2023), and literature reviews (Marchildon, 2019b, Witesman, 2020, Scarffe et al., 2022, Sapkota et al., 2023, Manns et al., 2024). Common across many of these methods is the use of quantitative indicators (health spending, life expectancy, public satisfaction) and qualitative insights (stakeholder interviews, thematic analyses) to examine the impacts of both centralized and decentralized governance on health system performance.

We developed two SWOT models to categorize and analyze data from these twelve papers, examining the pros and cons of centralization and decentralization. The value of each contributing factor must be weighed by policymakers based on the needs and characteristics of their unique system delivery environment.

Canada's History of Decentralization

Canada is one of the world's most decentralized federations, with a considerable amount of political and policy power being wielded by its ten provinces and three territories (Martin et al., 2018). The 1867 Constitution assigned hospitals, healthcare services, insurance, training, and professional regulation to the provinces, giving them primary responsibility for healthcare (Marchildon, 2019a; Tiedemann, 2019). The Canada Health Act (CHA) was enacted in 1984, with the primary goal of ensuring that all Canadians can access medically necessary hospital and physician services under consistent terms and conditions, without facing financial or other barriers (Tiedemann, 2019). The federal government uses the CHA along with the Canada Health Transfer (CHT) to ensure that provinces and territories adhere to the five criteria (public administration, comprehensiveness, universality, portability and accessibility) and two conditions (information be sent to the federal Minister of Health, and recognition of the transfer in public documents) in order to receive the full transfer of federal funds (Tiedemann, 2019).

In the 1980s, the World Health Organization (WHO) created decentralization recommendations based on the Alma-Ata Declaration to improve healthcare access in

underserved rural areas globally (Abimbola et al., 2019). The movement in Canada towards health system decentralization began in the early 1990s with the concept of creating regional health authorities (RHA) within provinces and territories to improve the integration of services across many diverse healthcare regions (Marchildon, 2019b).

Lessons from Alberta's Healthcare Reforms

In 1994, Alberta established 17 Regional Health Authorities (RHAs), reducing them to 9 in 2003 to streamline the system and enhance accountability (Marchildon, 2019a). By 2008, these RHAs were consolidated into the centralized Alberta Health Services (AHS) system through the Regional Health Authorities Act (Jarvis et al., 2023). In 2011, AHS was restructured into five administrative zones serving different geographical regions (Jarvis et al., 2023), and by 2024, further decentralization led to the creation of four specialized agencies for acute care, primary care, mental health and addictions, and continuing care (Bellefontaine, 2024).

Health system reorganizations like the ones in Alberta are large undertakings, which can lead to unanticipated outcomes. The rationale for centralization is focused on achieving cost savings through efficiency improvements aimed at administration, the consolidation of roles and decision-making power (Jarvis et al., 2023). As the interviews conducted by Jarvis et al demonstrated, there were several unintended consequences of these consolidation efforts, including the de-prioritization of preventative public health services, loss of workforce, decreased

local collaboration, and poor employee morale. Alberta's centralized system faced efficiency challenges, role confusion, and only slightly lower administrative costs per capita than the Canadian average (Scarffe et al., 2022). A careful evaluation of centralization and decentralization models can help policymakers assess risks and tailor solutions to meet the unique healthcare needs of their constituents before implementing costly provincial reforms.

Trends

The decentralization of healthcare systems to improve health outcomes and delivery performance (Sapkota et al., 2023) is on the rise globally among OECD countries between 2008 and 2018 (Dougherty et al., 2022). In a study conducted using OECD surveys carried out in 2008, 2012, 2016, and 2018, countries were asked to rate the degree to which the government is involved in thirteen policy or service areas, from 0-6, with 0 being completely centralized and 6 being completely decentralized to local governments (Dougherty et al., 2022), (See figure 1). These policy and service areas included outlining which level of government is responsible for allocation of resources, funding and budget decisions, remuneration of physicians, and setting public health goals (Dougherty et al., 2022).

Figure 1 highlights Canada's high level of decentralization globally, with a recent shift toward centralization in some provinces, including Alberta, Ontario, Quebec (Jarvis et al., 2023), Nova Scotia, Saskatchewan, and the Northwest Territories (Marchildon, 2019b). Debates emerged in these provinces and territories over decentralization, undermining local innovation

sustainability, equitable regional access, and efficient service delivery due to duplication and redundancy, prompting some jurisdictions to centralize administrative and fiscal responsibility for health service provision (Scarffe et al., 2022).

Figure 1

“Degree of ‘decentralisation’ scores by country, 2008 and 2018”

Note: The vertical axis is the decentralisation index, from the most centralised (0) to most decentralized (6).

(Dougherty et al., 2022, p.708)

SWOT Analysis

Utilizing a SWOT analysis in this literature review provides a structured framework to distill the many strengths, weaknesses, opportunities, and threats associated with both centralized

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and decentralized healthcare models. These dynamics are graphically represented in Figures 2 and 3, revealing how centralized systems can achieve benefits such as economies of scale, standardization, and cohesive decision-making, while also potentially limiting local responsiveness and innovation. Conversely, the SWOT for decentralization illustrates its strengths in fostering innovation in the idea generation stage and flexibility to respond to local needs, alongside risks of fragmentation and uneven resource allocation. These tables highlight the inherent trade-offs, and potential complementary roles of each governance approach.

Table 1

SWOT Analysis of Centralization

SWOT Analysis of Centralization	
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Standardization and consistency • Cost-savings • Economies of scale • Efficient resource distribution • Uniform service quality Clear chain of command for decision-making • Consolidated administration • Enhanced coordination of services • Consistent care pathways • Equal access to services • Rapid diffusion of innovation 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Bureaucratic rigidity • Slow to respond to local challenges • Detachment from local needs • Marginalization of local voices • Administrative bottlenecks • Limited contribution from frontline staff • Suppresses innovation (idea generation) • One-size-fits-all approach • May erode local stakeholder engagement • Could worsen disparities • Cuts may weaken public health operations • Potential for decreased accountability
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Unified electronic medical record system • Potential for stronger oversight, Implementation of clear performance standards • Improved coordination across the system 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Employee resistance to reforms due to a lack of autonomy • Local stakeholder resistance • Health challenges that require a rapid response

Table 2

SWOT Analysis of Decentralization

SWOT Analysis of Decentralization	
Strengths	Weaknesses
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Local autonomy for decision-making • Flexibility to respond quickly to local needs • Collaborative health system planning • Customizable to local needs. Enhanced innovation through idea generation • Promotes community engagement • Patient-centered care • Increased patient satisfaction • Facilitates testing of pilot projects 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Duplication of administrative roles • Inefficient service delivery • Increased spending • Inconsistent performance • Dependent on local skills and capacities • Difficulties with system-wide integration • Variability can lead to inequities • Communication silos • Challenges with health data-sharing • Gaps in service availability • If excessive, it can lead to fragmentation • If excessive, it can limit the spread of innovation
Opportunities	Threats
<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Potential to create mutual oversight between government levels • Potential for increased accountability from multiple levels • Expanding the decision-making space for locals • Enhanced innovation to solve localized problems 	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Professional brain-drain to other regions • Regional financial disparities can affect health outcomes • Poorly designed systems can create too much competition between regions • Potential conflicts between levels of government

Values

Public administrators advocating for structural reform are frequently guided by distinct sets of public values. For instance, values like accountability, uniformity, cost-savings, power, and efficiency (Scarffe et al., 2022, Manns et al., 2024) tend to support a centralized governance model, while responsiveness, community engagement, and local decision-making autonomy (Witesman, 2020, Durmus, 2024) are associated with decentralization. Both systems value innovation, with centralization supporting its diffusion and decentralization fostering idea generation (Scarffe et al., 2022).

In practice, the design of public administration structures often reflects these value-based norms, with each approach offering its own advantages for achieving specific public objectives, yet also presenting unique vulnerabilities to corruption (Witesman, 2020). Witesman further suggests that structural reforms are often seen as a pendulum shifting between centralization and decentralization, yet research indicates they can function as complementary systems.

How much is too much?

Decentralization has a complex impact on healthcare spending and life expectancy. According to Dougherty et al. (2022), when decentralization is moderate life expectancy is higher and public healthcare cost is lower. However, when decentralization becomes excessive, costs increase, and health outcomes decline. This suggests that while decentralization can enhance

efficiency and incentives, if excessive it may undermine effective healthcare delivery. These findings align with previous research and help explain why some countries have shifted toward a more balanced approach to healthcare governance. Figure 4 illustrates the non-linear, 'fish-shaped' relationship between costs (% of total health care spending per capita) and life expectancy (months), showing that the optimal healthcare system is moderately decentralized (5 out of 6) (Dougherty et al., 2022). When systems are excessively decentralized, they are prone to fragmentation (Martin et al., 2018, Dougherty et al., 2022) and organizational silos (Marchildon, 2019b), which can limit effective communication and the diffusion of innovation (Martin et al., 2018).

Figure 2

“Marginal effect of decentralisation on public spending on health care and life expectancy”

(Dougherty et al., 2022, p.712)

Communication

Decentralization impacts communication within healthcare systems in multiple ways. Sapkota et al. (2023) note that health information systems remain underexplored, with limited data and a lack of quantitative indicators making assessment difficult. Three reviews highlight challenges such as declining data quality, incomplete records, underreporting of health outcomes, and insufficient technical capacity, all of which weaken health information management and communication. Despite these challenges, Abimbola et al. (2019) argue that decentralized governance strengthens decision-making by bringing it closer to the people, improving the use of local knowledge, feedback, and control. This proximity enhances information exchange and enables more responsive rule-making, enforcement, and adaptation to local realities.

Decentralization's impact on communication extends beyond health information systems to the relationships between organizations themselves. Blanken et al. (2022) highlight that while the overall structure of the healthcare networks they studied remained stable, the connections within them shift significantly over time. Following decentralization, information exchange structures take longer than three years to reorganize, challenging prior assumptions about network stabilization. This instability undermines policy goals aimed at strengthening collaboration and, as seen in other sectors, weakens social capital and service sustainability. Given the importance of knowledge-based information exchange, maintaining stable communication is essential for effective interprofessional collaboration and integrated care. This demonstrates the long-term effects that policy reforms can have on healthcare communication networks.

Relevance and Opportunities for Further Research

This paper's findings are especially relevant for Canadian policymakers, as they reveal the trade-offs between centralized and decentralized models while suggesting that a moderate level of decentralization may achieve the best balance between efficiency and health outcomes. Future research should use a longitudinal approach to track changes over time and examine patient and provider-level impacts. Additionally, mixed methods studies that focus on the role of communication, including information sharing between organizations and community engagement, would provide valuable insights into governance outcomes.

Conclusion

This review reveals that neither centralized nor decentralized governance models offer a universal solution for Canadian healthcare. While centralized systems deliver economies of scale, uniformity, and efficient resource management, they may fall short in addressing local needs and fostering innovation. On the other hand, decentralized models, although they promote responsiveness, customized service delivery, and enhanced local input, can lead to fragmentation, communication challenges, and inefficiencies when taken to an extreme.

Lessons from historical reforms, such as the evolving healthcare structure in Alberta, highlight the complexities and unintended consequences of structural changes. The SWOT

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analyses emphasize the multitude of risks and benefits associated with each governance style. Evidence suggests that a moderate level of decentralization may offer the best framework for advancing public health based on desired outcomes and public values. For Canadian policymakers, these findings advocate for a hybrid approach that makes use of the strengths of both governance models while reducing their weaknesses. Future research, particularly using longitudinal and mixed methods studies that focus on communication and stakeholder engagement, is essential to refine these insights and support sustainable, high quality healthcare delivery for all Canadians.

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